

Sorption of mercury(II) by an adsorbent derived from fruit shell of *Terminalia catappa*

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Abstract : A carbon sorbent derived from the fruit shell of Indian almond (*Terminalia catappa*) by sulphuric acid treatment was used for the removal of mercury(II) from aqueous solution. Maximum uptake occurred in the pH range of 5 to 6. The kinetics of sorption conformed well to modified second order model among the other kinetic models (pseudo first order and pseudo second order) tested. The Langmuir isotherm defined the equilibrium data more precisely compared to Freundlich isotherm and the monolayer sorption capacity determined was 94.43 mg g⁻¹ at pH 5.0 and at room temperature (305 K). Sorption capacity increased with increase in temperature and the thermodynamic parameters, ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° , indicated the Hg^{II} sorption to be endothermic and spontaneous with a greater affinity of Hg^{II} species for the sorbent. About 60% of Hg^{II} was recovered from the spent carbon at pH 1.0, while 94% was desorbed using 1.0% KI solution.

Keywords : Adsorption, *Terminalia catappa*, mercury(II), kinetics, isotherms.

The importance of removing mercury from water and wastewater is well documented¹. Though the flux of mercury into the aquatic system has declined in recent years, there is still a lack of an effective, cheap means of treating mercury-containing wastewaters. The use of indigenously available agricultural or industrial wastes could be a potential alternative to conventional adsorbents. Waste materials like peanut hull², jackfruit peel³, coirpith⁴ and flax shive⁵ have been used as carbonaceous precursors for the removal of mercury. Normally the precursor material is heated to high temperatures (700–1200 °C) to remove the volatile matter and the resulting carbon is then activated either physically or chemically⁶. Carbonisation can also be performed by dehydration with sulphuric acid or phosphoric acid at low temperature resulting in a colloidal and porous active charcoal⁷. Such carbons have been reported⁸ to have the capability of decolourising dyes and ion exchange metal species.

In this work, the fruit of *Terminalia catappa*, commonly called as 'Indian almond', has been used as a carbonaceous precursor for its application in removing mer-

cury from aqueous solution. The portion of the fruit (excluding the kernel), which amounts to 89.68% of the total fruit, was chosen that comprises of a fibrous covering (8.97%), husk (34.08%) and hard endocarp (46.63%)⁹. Apart from the natural biological cycle, significant amount of fruit shell is discarded as a waste agricultural biomass, as this tree has many timber applications. A systematic study on the sorption of mercury(II) from aqueous solution as a function of pH, contact time, initial concentration, temperature and carbon dose was conducted by batch mode.

Results and discussion

Influence of pH :

The pH of the solution plays a vital role in any adsorption process and Fig. 1 illustrates the influence of pH on Hg^{II} adsorption. The removal of Hg^{II} increased with increase in pH and reached a shoulder-like maximum at pH 6.0 followed by a sharp increase in removal reaching close to 100% over the pH range of 7.0 to 10.0.

The observed increase in Hg^{II} removal from 6.6 to

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Fig. 1. Solution pH influence on Hg^{II} adsorption by TCC.

64.3% on increasing the pH from 1.0 to 6.0 can be explained as follows : According to stability constant calculations¹⁰, in the presence of Cl⁻, the predominant species at pH < 4.0 is HgCl₂. The formation of HgCl₂ has been found to decrease the Hg^{II} adsorption onto a commercial FS-400 GAC¹¹. Accordingly, Hg^{II} adsorption on TCC decreased when the pH was lowered using HCl from 6.0 to 1.0. Another plausible explanation can be : At low pH values excess H⁺ ions present in solution competes with Hg^{II} ions for active sites leading to less Hg^{II} removal. However when the pH was increased the concentration of H⁺ ions decreases, but the concentration of Hg^{II} ions remains the same leading to increased uptake. Similar trend was observed for the adsorption of Hg^{II} onto coir pith carbon⁴.

The sharp increase in Hg^{II} removal beyond pH 6.0 is due to the precipitation of Hg^{II} which leads to a quantitative removal close to 100% over the pH range of 7.0 to 10.0. Therefore to ensure the removal of Hg^{II} by TCC is only due to adsorption, in all further studies the solution pH was maintained at 5.0. An optimum pH of 6.5 was chosen for Hg^{II} sorption study on flax shive carbon⁵ as precipitation of Hg^{II} was observed above pH 7.0.

Agitation time influence and adsorption kinetics :

The kinetic data revealed an increase in adsorption

capacity with increase in time reaching a value of 82.93 mg g⁻¹ at an equilibrium time of 720 min. The kinetic data obtained was fitted with the following kinetic models like pseudo first order¹² (eq. 1), pseudo second order¹³ (eq. 2) and modified second order¹⁴ (eq. 3) kinetic models to find out the kinetic model that best describes the experimental data.

$$q_t = q_e [1 - \exp(-k_1 t)] \tag{1}$$

$$q_t = \frac{t}{(1/k_2 q_e^2) + (t/q_e)} \tag{2}$$

$$q_t = q_e \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{1}{\beta_2 + k_2 t} \right] \right\} \tag{3}$$

where q_e and q_t are the amounts of Hg^{II} adsorbed (mg g⁻¹) at equilibrium and at time t (min), respectively, k_1 and k_2 are the first order and second order rate constants (min⁻¹), respectively and β_2 is a constant that represents initial particle loading. Modeling was done by nonlinear optimization method that involves Marquardt-Levenberg algorithm¹⁵ using GNUPLOT program (Version 3.7 for MS Windows) and fitted parameters of the kinetic models obtained are presented in Table 1. The fitted curves of the models along with the experimental data for comparison are illustrated in Fig. 2. To have a measure of

Fig. 2. Fitted curves of the kinetic models with the experimental data.

Table 1. Fitted kinetic models for adsorption of Hg^{II} on TCC with r^2 and Δq values

Kinetic model	Fitted parameters	r^2	Δq (%)
Pseudo first order	$[q_t = 82.82 [1 - \exp(-0.0052t)]$	0.995	16.62
Pseudo second order	$q_t = \frac{t}{\left(1 / \left(0.5 \times 10^{-4}\right)\right) (105.17)^2 + (t / 105.17)}$	0.997	10.67
Modified second order	$q_t = 110.42 \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{1}{1.04 + 0.0043t} \right] \right\}$	0.999	1.46

degree of fitness the correlation coefficient, r^2 and normalized standard deviation, Δq (%), (using eq. 4) were computed and are presented in Table 1.

$$\Delta q(\%) = 100 \times \sqrt{\frac{\sum [(q_{ex} - q_{pr}) / q_{ex}]^2}{(n - 1)}} \quad (4)$$

where q_{ex} and q_{pr} are experimental and predicted equilibrium adsorption capacity data, respectively and n is the number of data points. Unlike, r^2 values, which are close to 1 for all the kinetic models, Δq values give a better picture of the kinetic fit. Relatively, higher Δq values obtained for modified second order model indicate that this kinetic model could more closely describe the experimental data than pseudo first order and pseudo second order models.

Adsorption isotherms :

The equilibrium data obtained were modeled with Freundlich¹⁶ (eq. 5) and Langmuir¹⁷ (eq. 6) isotherm equations.

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n} \quad (5)$$

$$q_e = \frac{Q_0 b C_e}{1 + b C_e} \quad (6)$$

where, K_F and n are Freundlich constants indicating the adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}) and intensity of adsorption, respectively, and Q_0 and b are Langmuir constants denoting the adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}) and energy of adsorption ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1}$), respectively. The fitted isotherm curves along with the experimental data for comparison are depicted in Fig. 3. On performing nonlinear optimization, the fitted parameters of Freundlich model, K_F and n , obtained were 38.25 mg g^{-1} and 4.0 , respectively and those of Langmuir model, Q_0 and b , were 94.43 mg g^{-1} and $0.49 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1}$, respectively. The r^2 and Δq values

Fig. 3. Fitted curves of the isotherm models with the experimental data.

calculated were 0.913 and 7.89 for Freundlich model and 0.996 and 1.94 for Langmuir model, respectively. The Langmuir model better described the equilibrium data than the Freundlich model, as the former showed a higher r^2 and lower Δq values than the latter. Using the best-fit Langmuir isotherm equation with fitted parameters, the volume of wastewater that could be treated was determined. If a wastewater contains Hg^{II} concentration of 5 mg dm^{-3} , 1 g of TCC can treat about 13 dm^3 of wastewater. As the equilibrium data conforms well to the basic Langmuir isotherm model, its assumptions, as detailed elsewhere¹⁷, holds good also for the present sorption system. In brief, the assumptions of Langmuir isotherm are :

maximum adsorption corresponds to a saturated monolayer (one molecule in thickness) of adsorbate molecules on the adsorbent surface, the energy of adsorption is constant and there is no transmigration of adsorbate in the plane of the surface.

The influence of isotherm shape on whether an adsorption process is 'favourable' or 'unfavourable' has been considered by Weber and Chakravorti¹⁸. The essential features of the Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless constant separation factor or equilibrium parameter¹⁹, R_L , defined as $1/(1 + bC_0)$, where b is Langmuir constant and C_0 is initial metal concentration (mg/L). The value of R_L indicates the shape of isotherm to be either unfavourable ($R_L > 1$) or linear ($R_L = 1$) or favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$). The R_L values obtained (Table 2) indicate favourable isotherm shape ($0 < R_L < 1$) for adsorption of Hg^{II} on TCC in the concentration range studied.

Table 2. The equilibrium parameter, R_L , values

Initial Hg ^{II} concentration C_0 (mg dm ⁻³)	R_L
5	0.2882
10	0.1684
20	0.0919
30	0.0632
40	0.0482
50	0.0389
60	0.0326

Influence of temperature – thermodynamic parameters :

The study on influence of temperature on Hg^{II} adsorption indicated the adsorption of Hg^{II} on TCC to be endothermic as the adsorption capacity increased with increase in the temperature of the system (Table 3). This may be attributed to the structural change that could have occurred on the adsorbent or may also be interpreted as 'activated diffusion', which can cause small pores to widen

and provide more surfaces for adsorption²⁰.

Thermodynamic parameters like change in enthalpy, ΔH° , change in entropy, ΔS° and change in free energy, ΔG° , were determined using the following relations²¹ :

$$K_c = \frac{C_{Ae}}{C_e} \tag{9}$$

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_c \tag{10}$$

$$\log K_c = \frac{\Delta S}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta H}{2.303RT} \tag{11}$$

where, K_c is the equilibrium constant, C_{Ae} is the solid phase concentration at equilibrium (mg dm⁻³), T is the temperature in Kelvin and R is the gas constant. The ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained from the slope and intercept of the van't Hoff plot of $\log K_c$ versus $1/T$ (Fig. 4) and are presented in Table 3. The positive value of ΔH° confirms the endothermic adsorption of Hg^{II} onto TCC. The positive value of ΔS° shows increased randomness at the solid-solution interface during Hg^{II} adsorption and reflects the affinity²² of TCC for Hg^{II} ions. The adsorbed water molecules, which are displaced by the adsorbate species, gain more translational entropy than is lost by the adsorbate molecules, thus allowing prevalence of randomness in the system²¹. The negative values of ΔG° and decrease in the magnitude of ΔG° with increase in temperature (Table 3) indicate the spontaneous nature of Hg^{II} adsorption on TCC at higher temperatures.

Influence of adsorbent dose :

Mercury(II) adsorption increased from 34.2 to 99.5% with increase in TCC dose from 0.05 to 5.0 g dm⁻³ (Fig. 5). This increasing trend is ascribed to the introduction of more binding sites for adsorption on increasing the carbon dose²³. A minimum amount of 4.0 g dm⁻³ of TCC was required for maximum Hg^{II} removal (98.6%) from 30 mg dm⁻³ solution. The results of this experiment were used to develop a mathematical relationship between percentage removal (R) and adsorbent dose (m , g dm⁻³)

Table 3. Temperature influence on adsorption capacity and thermodynamic parameters

Temperature (K)	q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	K_c	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
305	82.75	16.55	0.88		
313	119.55	23.91	-1.03		
				83.03	268.78
323	155.85	31.17	-3.39		
333	184.00	36.80	-6.76		

Fig. 4. van't Hoff plot for determination of ΔH° and ΔS° .

Fig. 5. Effect of carbon dose on Hg^{II} adsorption by TCC.

by nonlinear optimization method. The relationship developed is as follows :

$$R = \frac{m}{1.45 \times 10^{-3} + 1.05 \times 10^{-2} m} \quad (12)$$

This equation can be used to predict the percentage Hg^{II} removal for any TCC dose within particular experimental conditions. The correlation coefficient, r^2 , obtained between the experimental and calculated percentage removal values was 0.99.

Desorption study :

Desorption study was conducted to recover the metal, to regenerate the spent carbon for repeated use and to recycle the metal-recovered wastewater. After performing adsorption experiments with 20 mg dm⁻³ of Hg^{II} solution and 0.2 g dm⁻³ of carbon dose at pH 5.0, the solutions were adjusted to different pH values from 1.0 to 6.0 and shaken for 1 h to find the effect of varying pH on desorption. The results are illustrated in Fig. 6 which shows that a maximum Hg^{II} desorption of 60% was achieved at pH 1.0.

In order to achieve complete desorption of Hg^{II} and envisaging the fact that Hg^{II} can form relatively stable iodide complexes than chloride complexes^{2,24}, three dif-

Fig. 6. Effect of pH on desorption of Hg^{II} from spent carbon.

ferent percentage solutions of KI (0.5, 1.0 and 2.0%) were tried as desorbing agents. About 85.2, 94.2 and 94.6% of Hg^{II} was recovered by using 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0% of KI solutions, which indicates that maximum Hg^{II} recovery was obtained by using a minimum of 1.0% KI solution.

The foregoing study has revealed the feasibility of using a carbon sorbent derived from the fruit shell of *Terminalia catappa* for the removal of mercury from aqueous solution. The carbonaceous precursor chosen being an inexpensive waste material the treatment is expected to be economical.

Experimental

Preparation and characterization of TCC : Fruit shell of *Terminalia catappa*, collected from Tiruchirappalli, India, was dried and chopped into small pieces. The chopped pieces were treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84) in a weight ratio of 1 : 0.92 (shell : acid) and the resulting black product was kept in an air oven maintained at 160 ± 5 °C. The carbon obtained was designated as TCC. The carbon was ground and the portion retained between 180 and 210 μm sieves were used. The carbon was characterized for physico-chemical properties like pH (6.14), moisture content (9.90%), bulk density (0.75 g cm^{-3}), ash content (1.72%), decolourising power (10.50 mg g^{-1}), ion exchange capacity²⁵ (0.93 meq. g^{-1}), water soluble matter (1.55%) and acid soluble matter (4.00%) according to ISI methods²⁶. The surface area ($4.60 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) was measured by nitrogen adsorption and calculated from the B.E.T. equation²⁷. The low surface area may be due to the presence of oxygen as complex in the form of C_xO_y ²⁸ that cannot be displaced by nitrogen used in the B.E.T.-N₂ method or may be due to the opportunity of micropores occurring in the structure is either very low or non-existent²⁹. Similar low values were observed for carbons prepared from coconut shell³⁰ ($13.00 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and flax shive²⁹ ($19.00 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) by sulphuric acid treatment.

Batch experiments : Sorption study was carried out by agitating 100 cm^3 of mercury(II) solution of predetermined concentration with a known amount of carbon in a orbital shaker (250 rpm). After defined time intervals, samples were withdrawn from the shaker, centrifuged and the supernatant solution was analysed for residual mercury(II) spectrophotometrically³¹ using rhodamine-6G as reagent in a Perkin-Elmer EZ 301 UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 575 nm. The kinetic study was conducted by agitating 30 mg dm^{-3} with 0.2 g dm^{-3} of carbon dose

for predetermined periods of time. The equilibrium study was carried out by agitating a range of mercury(II) concentration ($5\text{--}60 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$) with 0.2 g dm^{-3} of carbon dose. For pH (1–10) and temperature (305, 313, 323 and 333 K) variation studies. 30 and 40 mg dm^{-3} of mercury(II) solution, respectively, was shaken with 0.2 g dm^{-3} of carbon dose for 12 h. The carbon dose study was carried out by equilibrating 30 mg dm^{-3} of mercury(II) solution with a range of carbon dose (0.05 to 5.0 g dm^{-3}) for 12 h. Experiments were repeated at least three times and mean values are reported. Standard deviations and analytical errors were calculated and the maximum error was $\pm 5\%$.

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References

1. F. Berglund and M. Bertin, "Chemical Fallout", Thomas Publishers, Springfield, 1969; C. R. Krishnamoorthi and P. Viswanathan, "Toxic Metal in the Indian Environment", Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., New Delhi, 1991.
2. C. Namasivayam and K. Periasamy, *Wat. Res.*, 1993, **27**, 1163.
3. B. Stephen Inbaraj and N. Sulochana in "Proc. 17th Int. Conf. Solid Waste Technol. Management", ed. Ronald L. Mersky, Widener University Press, Philadelphia, 2001, p. 802.
4. C. Namasivayam and K. Kadirvelu, *Carbon*, 1999, **37**, 79.
5. M. Cox, E. I. El-Shafey, A. A. Pichugin and Q. Appleton, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, 2000, **75**, 427.
6. M. Smisek and S. Cerny, "Active Carbon", Elsevier, London, 1970, p. 10.
7. C. L. Mantell, "Industrial Carbon", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 1946, p. 116.
8. B. Stephen Inbaraj and N. Sulochana, *Bioresource Technol.*, 2004, **94**, 49; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1; *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2002, **9**, 201; B. Stephen Inbaraj, K. Selvarani and N. Sulochana, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 2002, **61**, 971; E. I. El-Shafey, M. Cox, A. A. Pichugin and Q. Appleton, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, 2002, **77**, 429.
9. "The Wealth of India - Raw Materials", ed. Y. R. Chadha, Publication and Information Directorate, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1985, p. 168.
10. W. R. Knocke and L. H. Hemphill, *Wat. Res.*, 1981, **15**, 275.
11. X. Ma, K. S. Subramanian, C. L. Chakravarti, R. Guo, J. Cheng, Y. Lu and W. F. Pickering, *J. Env. Sci. Hlth.*, 1992, **27**, 1389.
12. S. Lagergren, *K. Sven. Vetenskapsakad. Handl.*, 1898,

- 24, 1.
13. Y. S. Ho and G. McKay, *Wat. Res.*, 2001, **35**, 605.
 14. A. G. Ritchie, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1997, **73**, 1650; C. W. Cheung, J. F. Porter and G. McKay, *Wat. Res.*, 2001, **35**, 605.
 15. D. W. Marquardt, *SIAM. J.*, 1963, **11**, 431; K. Levenberg, *Qty. Appl. Math.*, 1944, **2**, 164.
 16. H. Freundlich, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1906, **57**, 384.
 17. I. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 1361.
 18. T. W. Weber and R. K. Chakravorti, *Am. Inst. Chem. Engrs.*, 1974, **20**, 228.
 19. K. R. Hall, L. C. Eagleton, A. Acrivos and T. Vermeulen, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Fund.*, 1966, **5**, 212.
 20. C. H. Giles, D. Smith and A. Huitson, *J. Colloid Int. Sci.*, 1974, **47**, 755.
 21. C. Namasivayam and R. T. Yamuna, *Environmental Pollution*, 1995, **89**, 1.
 22. B. P. Kelleher, M. O'Callaghan, M. K. Leahy, T. F. O'Dwyer and J. J. Leahy, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, 2002, **77**, 1212; Y. S. Ho, T. H. Chiang and Y. M. Hsueh, *Process Biochem.*, 2005, **40**, 119.
 23. K. Kadirvelu, B. Brasquet and P. Le Cloirec, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 2407.
 24. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 1973, p. 503.
 25. G. H. Jeffery, J. Basset, J. Mendham and R. C. Denny, "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 5th ed., ELBS Publication, London, 1989.
 26. ISI, "Methods of Sampling and Tests for Activated Carbon used for Decolourising Vegetable Oils and Sugar Solutions", Indian Standards Institution, New Delhi, 1977, IS : 877.
 27. S. Brunauer, P. H. Emmet and E. Teller, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 309.
 28. C. P. Huang, in "Carbon Adsorption Handbook", eds. P. N. Cheremisinoff and F. Ellerbush, Ann Arbor Science, Ann Arbor, MI, 1978, p. 281.
 29. M. Cox, E. I. El-Shafey, A. A. Pichugin and Q. Appleton, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, 1999, **74**, 1019.
 30. K. Muthukumar, "Studies on Chemically Activated Carbon for the Removal of Trace Inorganics from Water", PhD Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Chennai, India, 1985.
 31. T. V. Ramakrishna, G. Aravamudan and M. Vijayakumar, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **84**, 369.